

D2.1: Prototype of a calendaring unit

<i>Authors (institution)</i>	Moises Espindola Rodriguez (FOM), Kristoffer Visti Graae (FOM)
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SUMMARY SHEET

<i>Project Acronym</i>	BATMACHINE
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<i>Project Coordinator</i>	Kamil Burak Dermenci kamil.burak.dermenci@vub.be Aitor Sánchez aitor.sanchez@vub.be VUB
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DISCLAIMER

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Project Overview

The BATMACHINE project is centred on strengthening Europe's battery cell industrial manufacturing value chain by developing new battery cell manufacturing machinery. This will be done while giving priority to minimising the energy for cell production, enhancing plant efficiency rates, and integrating intelligent control processes to reduce scrap.

The project will develop and implement an optimised and energy-efficient process chain considering:

- Slurry mixing (automated modular process set-up including monitoring techniques).
- Exclusive slot-die coating and drying novel machinery (with one side coating, a coating speed of 1m/min up to 20m/min and a web-width of 300 mm).
- A calendaring tool to be integrated in a battery manufacturer for process optimisation.

Moreover, intelligent control processes and Industry 4.0 will be intensively integrated through the creation of a collaborative and FAIR data space for battery production. Digital interfaces between battery manufacturing equipment, control system, and engineers will be developed with the aim of building universal digitalisation tools to enhance the battery production and create a battery passport. The environmental and economic impact of different machinery, production line configurations and factory designs will be deeply studied to reduce the cost and energy consumption of manufacturing processes.

List of Participants

1		VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	VUB	Belgium
2		FUNDACION TEKNIKER	TEKNIKER	Spain
3		SKZ-KFE GGMBH	SKZ	Germany
4		FOM TECHNOLOGIES A/S	FOM	Denmark
5		DEEP BLUE SRL	DBL	Italy
6		NETZSCH FEINMAHLTECHNIK GMBH	NFT	Germany
7		RHEINISCH-WESTFAELISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE AACHEN	RWTH AACHEN	Germany
8		SINTEF AS	SINTEF	Norway
8a		SINTEF OCEAN AS	SINTEF- OCEAN	Norway
9		POMEGA ENERJI DEPOLAMA TEKNOLOJILERI ANONIM SIRKETI	POMEGA	Turkey
10		CEGASA ENERGIA S.L.U.	CEGASA	Spain
11		LECLANCHÉ GMBH	LEC	Germany

Document Change Log

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1.0	24/10/2024	RWTH review, Pabitra Saha	General review
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1.2	25/10/2024	VUB	Final check before submission

ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	Extended
GUI	Graphic User Interface
FAT	Factory Acceptance Test
WP	Work Package
IR lamp	Infra-red lamp

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Executive summary

The objective of “D2.1: Prototype of a calendaring unit” is to present publicly **FOM BATMACHINE calendaring unit**, its technical data, its control interface, with a series of validation tests of all mechanical components (rollers, gear box, ..), electrical components (encoder/speed, e-stop), and control and communication interfaces.

In this document, we also demonstrate the calendaring unit as a whole, ensuring the unit meets the necessary requirements for standalone use with preliminary calendaring tests results with different battery anode electrodes.

Chapter 2 contains the technical description of the unit, the site requirements, its parts with a brief description and its dimensions.

Chapter 3 presents the Factory Acceptance Tests (FAT) phase to ensure the Calendaring unit meets the technical requirements that were proposed during different previous development periods. We present a series of thorough tests conducted by FOM, the manufacturer, at FOM research facilities before the equipment gets shipped to BATMACHINE partners. In both chapters 2 and 3 we emphasize the technical successful achievements, and they pave the way for a smoother installation and commissioning process.

Chapter 4 details functional tests or demonstration actions performed with the FOM BATMACHINE calendaring unit; it provides a comprehensive assessment of the calendaring unit quality and performance.

The FOM BATMACHINE calendaring unit presented here is a prototype, and a feedback loop will start with the BATMACHINE partners, based on their expectations, experience and calendaring results. We are confident that the results of the tests presented herein will enable the acceptance of the calendaring unit to FOM potential customers.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

This deliverable (D2.1) of task 2.3 of work package 2 “Electrode Machinery Development” is a demonstration public deliverable. The FOM BATMACHINE calendaring unit is a FOM new product, the main result of T2.3 and the demonstration subject of this deliverable.

The demonstration activities are unfolded in two groups, first a Factory Acceptance Test (FAT) and then demonstration actions. FAT acts as a critical checkpoint before any machinery leaves FOM’s factory floor. The calendaring demonstration actions consist of a few calendaring tests done to battery electrodes using FOM’s slurries or BATMACHINE partners’ slurries in both cases, slot-die coated by FOM.

During the FAT, FOM prepared the operation and maintenance manual to be followed by the users. FAT actions are tailored to demonstrate technical aspects important to potential users, and to validate the mechanical, electrical and control interfaces.

2. Description of equipment

The FOM BATMACHINE calendaring unit is unique on its web width handling of up to 350 mm, its gap setting using four lasers, the possibility to preheat the electrodes via an IR lam, its compact design on a work cabinet with wheels and its plug-and-play installation.

2.1 Calendaring unit specifications

Table 1. Calendaring unit technical specifications

Parameter	Value
Calendaring speed	0.1-2 m/min
Calendaring width	≤ 350 mm
Maximum load per side	20 kN
Substrate	Flexible
Substrate heating	IR lamp optional
Drive unit	Servo motor
Gap setting accuracy	± 3 μm
Calendaring gap adjustment	Manual handwheel
Maximum gap	1.5 mm

2.2 Calendaring unit site requirements

Table 2. Calendaring unit site requirements

Parameter	Value
Dimensions: (WxLxH)	900 x 625 x 630 mm ³
Mass	500 kg
Supply voltage (Un)	(1+N) 85 ... 264 V a.c. Supply
Frequency (Hz)	50/60
Nominal Current (In)	5 A
Short Circuit Strength (Isc)	5 kA
Protection (maximum size)	C16 A
Cable (minimum area)	2.5 mm ²
Line system	Grounded WYE / TN-S

The contents of Table 2 show that the Calendaring unit is a plug and play machine, since all site requirements are readily available in any laboratory.

2.3 Calendaring unit parts description

The exterior of the machine consists of the following parts. Figure 1 shows the loading side of the machine.

- 1. Upper laser sensors:** Is the mounting position of the two point-lasers measuring the relative distance between them and the top roll upper part.
- 2. Lifting points:** Use to position the calendar in the wheeled frame.
- 3. Upper and lower roller:** The essential part of the calendar, the distance between them determines the calendaring gap.
- 4. IR lamp:** Not included. Optional component to preheat the electrodes before they enter the calendaring gap. Max. temperature is 200°C.
- 5. Gap adjustment gear box:** It changes the speed and direction of the rotation applied to the gap adjustment handles to move the bottom roll up and down.
- 6. Gap adjustment handles.** Rotating both handles in **counter clockwise direction** lowers only the bottom roll. Rotating the handles in clockwise direction moves only the bottom roll up.

- 7. Unprocessed coated foil:** The depicted foil or electrode rests in the loading tray in the inlet side of the machine.
- 8. Handles rotation lock.** Consists of two hand screws to prevent or allow the rotation of the gap adjustment handles.
- 9. Force measurement sensor.** It is not visible in the image; it is located in the right side of the top roll to measure the force during calendaring.

Figure 1: Inlet side of machine. Protective covers and GUI not shown for explanatory reasons

Figure 2 shows the outlet side of the machine.

Figure 2: Outlet side of machine.

1. **Outlet side protective covers.** Two independent metallic covers that should be removed only when the machine is power off and disconnected from the electricity supply for cleaning purposes after work.
2. **Lower laser sensors.** Is the mounting position of the two point-lasers measuring the relative distance between them and the bottom roll lower part.
3. **Force measurement sensor.** It is not visible in the image; it is located in the left side of the top roll to measure the force during calendaring.
4. **Gear motor.** It is a torque multiplier and speed reduction box to achieve a wide range of calendaring speeds.

With the FOM Standalone Calendaring unit, an accompanying electrical cabinet is included.

Figure 3: Labeled photo of the FOM Standalone Calendaring unit electrical cabinet.

1. **GUI:** This is the Graphic User Interface of the calendaring unit.
2. **Internet port.** This port is used to provide internet to the Calendaring unit for remote support.
3. **Machine ethernet port:** This port is used to establish communication with the machine, only to be used by FOM service team.
4. **Main power switch.** It is the main and only power switch of the Calendaring unit. Used to reset the machine and power it ON and OFF.

2.4 Calendaring unit dimensions

Figure 4. Top view calendaring machine

Figure 5. Front view calendaring machine

3 Factory Acceptance Tests

Table 3 describes the various tests the BATMACHINE Calendaring unit was subjected to, along with some early recommendations for improvements for future versions.

Table 3. FAT completion points.

Test No.	Test to be performed	Passed	Not Passed	Tested By
1	Test supply disconnecting machine by switching on and off. In off Position all electrical supply to control equipment shall be isolated, selected electrical points are measured and checked that no electrical voltage is present. In On Position, all electrical components shall be electrically supplied, and CPI, OP, etc.. Shall automatically go into RUN mode.	x		MOS
2	Confirm external safety plates are in place from loading and unloading sides.	x		MOS
3	Confirm internal safety guard is in place from the loading side.	x		MOS
4	Confirm the software can be engaged and the green light turns on.	x		MOS
5	Confirm software can be turned off with power button.	x		MOS
6	Confirm current force left readout	x		MOS
7	Confirm current force right readout	x		MOS
8	Confirm max force setpoint can be edited.	x		MOS
9	Confirm absolute value for bottom roll right follows handles labels.	x		MOS
10	Confirm absolute value for bottom roll left follows handles labels.	x		MOS
11	Confirm laser measurement can be zero	x		MOS
12	Confirm initial gap set point can be established	x		MOS
13	Confirm that speed can be adjusted at different speeds	x		MOS
14	Confirm setpoint speed readout	x		MOS
15	Confirm current speed readout	x		MOS
16	Confirm minimum speed can be reached 0.1m/min	x		MOS
17	Inspect web speed for smooth motion, at 0.1m/min, 0.5m/min & 1m/min	x		MOS
18	Test of jog forward direction with GUI & quick function buttons.	x		MOS
19	Test of jog reverse direction with GUI.	x		MOS
20	Confirm jog speed can be edited to max 2 m/min.	x		MOS

21	Check that alarm history can be read. Confirm that history of events can also be seen.	x		MOS
22	General visual inspection of all (Graphic User Interface) GUI screens. Look for misalignments, colour deviations, font deviations etc..	x		MOS
23	Emergency stop functions shall disconnect electrical supply to equipment according to risk assessment (Motion). All movements must come to a half within 2 seconds.	x		MOS
24	Check that E-stops turns red light on	x		MOS
25	Check that E-stops alarm can be reset, and power is restored after reset. Confirm alarm is shown in alarm list.	x		MOS
26	Confirm that demonstration of calendaring electrodes has been completed	x		MOS
27	Confirm Max force alarm is operational	x		MOS
28	Confirm read out speed matches set point speed during calendaring	x		MOS
29	Confirm force readout right and left during calendaring	x		MOS
30	Confirm initial gap set point is preserved after calendaring test	x		MOS
31	Confirm that the electrical drawing pack is printed and present in the back of the electrical panel.	x		MOS
32	Confirm that all labels and pictograms are present	x		MOS
33	Confirm that working space around the machine is sufficient	x		MOS
34	Document pictures and videos of the machine, working environment	x		MOS
35	Confirm that electrical panel sections are tidy and clean	x		MOS

Test No. 30 was not passed at the time of writing the first version of this document. Corrective measures were taken to improve it, including re-marching both rollers to improve the run-out accuracy of the rollers to $\pm 3 \mu\text{m}$ and software features to make it easier to calibrate the calendaring gap.

4 Demonstration actions

FOM Technologies Science team made battery anode electrodes, using a generic inhouse battery anode recipe with two objectives:

- Test the Calendaring Unit prototype under real conditions and,
- Provide battery anode electrode samples to our BATMACHINE partners from Task 2.2 (Coating and Drying), in particular to SKZ as they will develop a thickness measurement technique.

4.1 Test Battery anode electrodes

The test electrodes were fabricated in a FOM Sigma R2R machine with copper foil (9 μm thick, 180 mm wide) using a generic battery anode slurry:

- 95% synthetic graphite from Sigma Adrich
- 2.4% SBR
- 2.4% CMC
- 38% dry matter content
- DI water as solvent

Table 4. Battery anode electrodes coatings to be delivered with the Calendaring unit.

Coating No.	Wet film thickness (μm)	Coating Width (cm)	Coating distance (m)	Slurry needed (mL)
7	100	10	5	50
8	200	10	5	100
9	250	10	5	125
10	150	10	5	75
11	120	10	5	60
12	120	10	3	36
13	200	16	5	160
14	200	16	5	160
15	250	16	4	160
16	150	16	5	120
17	120	16	7	134,4
13	200	16	5	160
14	200	16	5	160
15	250	16	4	160
16	150	16	5	120
17	120	16	7	134,4

In slot-die coating, the wet film thickness is directly proportional to the slurry flow rate and inversely proportional to the coating speed and the coating width (how wide the

battery electrode is, perpendicular to the coating direction). For the purpose of calendaring test, only the coating width and the thickness are relevant.

4.2 Calendaring test on battery anode electrodes

Table 5. Parameters of battery anode electrodes before and after calendaring.

Coating No.	Coating Width (cm)	Force (kN)	Speed (m/min)	Gap selected (μm)	Before Thickness (μm)	After Thickness (μm)
17	16	20	n/a	70	85	-
17A	16	20	0.1	50	83	74
17B	16	20	0.2	40	85	75
17D	16	20	0.5	40	83	-
17E	16	20	0.2	60	85	75

The results from Table 5 show the thickness of the battery electrode No.17 (from Table 4), before and after the calendaring process. The thickness values were obtained using a Mitutoyo handheld digital micrometer and measured around 1 cm from the coating edge.

For all cases the max force setpoint was 20 kN, what means that the real force applied to the electrode was less than 20 kN. For example, in the case of calendaring at 0.5 m/min, the alarm “Max Force Reached” is triggered, meaning that the necessary force to calendar the electrode to 40 μm is more than 20 kN (per side). The calendaring process was not achieved, and thus the thickness after calendaring is not reported.

Force, speed (Figure 6) and gap are set point parameters and can also be read out and will be written in a digital file as part of coating, drying and calendaring ontology data.

Figure 6. Calendaring unit operation screen showing the set point and read out speed values. In the figure, the current speed (read out) is 0.00 m/min because the rolls are not moving.

Figure 7. Inlet side of the Calendaring unit with a 160mm coating width battery electrode being calendared.

Note the protective covers in Figure 7 preventing the user to approach their fingers to the rollers. Even if the protective covers are taken off for cleaning, the user will encounter a safety bar shown in Figure 1 behind the options IR lamp. That bar cannot be removed.

Figure 8 shows coating No. 17E: the calendared is electrode displayed on the left side, while the right side represents the coated (i.e. non calendared) electrode. It can be seen that the surface of the electrode is smoother, typical of a calendared electrode however a more in-depth analysis will be done by other BATMACHINE partners with great expertise in battery electrodes characterization.

Figure 8. Photograph showing in the right (14-16 cm) a non-calendared section of an electrode and to the left (10.5- 12.5 cm) a calendared section with 17E parameters.

Table 6. Micrographs of Battery electrodes. The image is around 2x2 mm².

Finally, Table 6 shows a series of micrographs of the electrode calendared using different parameters. It shows how the roughness of the electrode is reduced and presumably also the porosity. It is only visual inspection of a small area of the electrode, as mentioned before, a deeper analysis is needed and will be performed during the duration of the project.

Table 7 shows macroscopic pictures of the same electrodes from Table 6 as seen by the naked eye. Just like in Figure 8, it can be seen that the electrode has gone through a calendaring process.

Table 7. Optical pictures of Battery electrodes calendared using different parameters. The picture captures around 2 cm of the electrode in the coating direction.

5 Conclusions

A technical summary of “D2.1 - Prototype of a calendaring unit” is presented in this document. The main objective is showcasing for the first time the FOM BATMACHINE calendaring unit, its technical specifications, its unique selling points, some of its interfaces and a few battery electrodes’ calendaring tests results. Extensive testing of the calendaring unit will take place at a BATMACHINE partner location, where the unit will be first sent.

During different previous development periods a series of technical specifications were agreed on with other BATMACHINE beneficiaries and can be found in Table 1; the calendaring unit we present herein fulfils all the requirements.

The new FOM BATMACHINE calendaring unit presented herein allows the user calendaring at a given calendaring gap, calendaring force and calendaring speed for as many meters it is needed. All parameters can be controlled and saved through an easy-to-use interface.

6 Deviations

The delivery of the prototype calendaring unit had to be delayed from May to October 2024, first due to the need of extra time to source components with a long lead time, and most recently to try fixing an issue we found during FAT related with the ability of the machine to preserve the calendaring gap after calendaring. This does not prevent

the user from calendaring, but the unit needs to be re-zeroed between calendaring processes.

7 Annexes

1. FOM Calendaring unit, Operation and Maintenance Manual.

FOM

TECHNOLOGIES

FOM Calendaring unit

OPERATION & MAINTENANCE MANUAL

Rev 1.1 – October 2024

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1. Introduction

This document serves as the operation and maintenance manual for the FOM Stand-alone Calendaring unit.

The FOM Standalone Calendaring unit is a tool designed for versatile use with flexible substrates where various types of slurry such as slot-die coated battery electrodes is deposited. This tool is engineered to calendar thin films comprising a wide array of solution-processed precursor materials onto a diverse range of coating substrates. With its user-friendly interface and precise control over web speed, gap thickness, force build-up and optional substrate heating, the FOM Standalone Calendaring unit is well-suited for research environments, enabling seamless transitions from lab-scale materials research to pilot-scale coating processes.

1.1. Revision history

Revision	Date	Change	Serial
1	01.10.2024	Full revision	-
1.1	14.10.2024	Spare parts and calibration revision	

In this current version, this manual applies only to the versions listed in the last line. Should you require a manual for a previous version, please, do not hesitate to contact us.

1.2. Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
HMI	Human-machine interface
PPE	Personal protective equipment
R2R	Roll-to-roll
SD	Slot-die
SDH	Slot-die head
TSV	Tab-separated values

1.3. Site requirements

Table 1: Site requirements

Parameter	Value
Dimensions: (WxLxH)	900 x 625 x 630 mm ³
Mass	500 kg
Supply voltage (Un)	(1+N) 85 ... 264 V a.c. Supply
Frequency (Hz)	50/60
Nominal Current (In)	5 A
Short Circuit Strength (Isc)	5 kA
Protection (maximum size)	C16 A
Cable (minimum area)	2.5 mm ²
Line system	Grounded WYE / TN-S

1.4. Calendaring unit specifications

Parameter	Value
Calendaring speed	0.1-2 m/min
Calendaring width	≤ 350 mm
Maximum load per side	20 kN
Substrate	Flexible
Substrate heating	N/A
Drive unit	Servo motor
Calendaring gap adjustment	Manual handwheel
Maximum gap	1.5 mm

1.5. Standards and normative

FOM Technologies declares that the product is lives up to the Machinery Directive 2006/42/EC and is designed and manufactured in compliance with the following standards:

Type A

ISO 12100:2011 – Safety of machinery – General principles for design – Risk assessment and risk reduction

DS/ISO/TR 14121-2:2012 – Safety of machinery – Risk assessment - Part 2: Practical guidance and examples of methods

Type B

EN ISO 13850:2015 – Safety of Machinery Emergency stop function – Principles for design

EN ISO 14120:2015 - Safety of Machinery – Guards – General principles for the design and construction of fixed and movable guards

EN ISO 13857:2019 – Safety of Machinery - Safety distances to prevent hazard zones being reached by upper and lower limbs.

EN ISO 13849-1:2023 - Safety of machinery – Safety-related parts of control systems – Part 1: General principles for design

EN ISO 13849-2:2014 - Safety of machinery – Safety-related parts of control systems – Part 2: Validation

DS/EN 60204-1:2018 - Safety of machinery – Electrical equipment on machines – Part 1: General requirements

1.6. Disclaimers & equipment hazards

To ensure the successful operation of the FOM Standalone Calendaring unit and prioritize the safety of all users, operators, trainees, and maintenance personnel should read and thoroughly understand this manual before initiating any experiments or tool maintenance. It is imperative that operators are in a state of sound mind and body when operating this equipment. The usage of this equipment should be restricted to authorized personnel and not extended to the general public.

It is recommended that new users receive proper training in the use of this equipment from experienced operators. Any deviation from the instructions provided in this manual may lead to personal and material damage, for which FOM Technologies A/S cannot be held responsible.

Before operating the device, the user must ensure the functional safety and the proper conditions of the machine and accessories. The device must not be operated if there is any visible damage.

1.6.1. Risks and hazards

Important: FOM Standalone Calendaring unit is equipped with an emergency stop button for the immediate halting of all machine operations. This button must be assessed once per year to guarantee its functionality.

The following table provides an overview of the risks and hazards associated with the operation of the FOM Standalone Calendaring unit machine.

Table 2: Risks and hazards associated with the use of the FOM Calendaring unit.

Hazard	Preventive measures or action plan
Burn	Operators should exercise caution and refrain from touching the heating parts when they are hot, as the temperature can be higher than 200 °C. It is important to note that even after the equipment has been shut down, the heated parts will remain hot for some time, posing a burn risk to operators even when power is not supplied to the tool. Wear adequate PPE before operating around hot surfaces.

Crushing/pinching

Machinery in motion poses a risk of injury as it can harm individuals. To ensure safety, operators must avoid placing their fingers, any other body parts, or loose clothing in the path of moving mechanisms. Potential damage to both objects and individuals may occur if caught in the motion paths of the components. In case of emergency the FOM Standalone Calendaring unit can be halted using the emergency stop button.

Electric shock

While the main power is being supplied, operators should refrain from touching the cables, plugs, and electrical cabinet. Even after the machine is turned off, a lethal high voltage can still be present. All electrical work must only be performed by qualified personnel, with adequate PPE.

Chemical exposure

The calendaring process involving certain inks and solvent evaporation have the potential to expose operators to hazardous chemical substances. Operators should be fully aware that they bear sole responsibility for understanding the risks associated with the use of these chemicals. It is strongly advised that operators consult the safety data sheet for each chemical substance and conduct a comprehensive chemical risk assessment.

1.6.2. Intended use

The equipment should be exclusively used for calendaring of battery electrodes or similar materials, in accordance with the instructions provided in this user manual. Engaging in unintended applications or making aftermarket modifications to the equipment not only carries the risk of equipment damage but also poses a threat to operator safety. It is important to note that such actions will void the warranty provided for the equipment.

2. Spare parts

The calendaring unit's spare parts are critical to maintaining uninterrupted operation and reducing downtime. To ensure efficiency, the parts are divided into two categories based on their lead time for delivery. This classification helps determine stocking needs, enable timely procurement, and prevent delays in maintenance or repair activities.

Category 1: Standard lead time

Parts that can be delivered within less than two weeks are assigned to Category 1. These parts are typically non-critical and easily sourced. These parts are marked with the color Green for easy identification.

Category 2: Extended lead time

Parts that take more than two weeks for delivery are assigned to Category 2. Due to longer procurement times, these parts may require advanced ordering. They are marked with the color Red and should be considered for stocking to prevent extended machine downtime.

Tabel 1. Categories for the spare parts

Category	Criteria	Colour
Category 1	Standard lead time. It takes less than 2 weeks to be delivered.	Green
Category 2	Extended lead time. It takes more than 2 weeks to be delivered.	Red

Tabel 2. Spare part list

Drawing No./Part No.	Designation	Quantity	Category
SKF-90VS-R	V ring seal	3	Red
LMGZ313.25000.65.H13.H15	FMS Force measuring bearing	1	Red
A1067091	Assembly bearing house	1	Red
P1067089	Bearing bushing \varnothing 140/120mm	1	Red
7213 BEGAP	Single angular contact ball bearing SKF-7213BEGAP	2	Red
SKF-PCM303440E	PTFE composite straight bushing	2	Green
SKF-24013-2RS5W-VT143	Spherical roller bearing	2	Green
A65-din471	Seegerring A65-din471	2	Red
ILD1220-25	Laser sensor ILD1220-25 (25-50mm)	2	Red
23410	Tension spring	1	Red
IGUS-GSM-2528-20	Bushing \varnothing 25/ \varnothing 28x20 (drilled)	2	Red
HG-KR73	Servomotor	1	Red
	Mitsubishi servo equipment	1	Red

3. Description of equipment

3.1. Calendaring unit parts description

The exterior of the machine consists of the following parts. The following image shows the loading side of the machine.

Figure 3-1: Inlet side of machine. Protective covers and GUI not shown for explanatory reasons

- 1. Upper laser sensors:** Used for measuring the relative distance between the sensor and the upper roller surface.

2. **Lifting points:** Use to position the calendar in the wheeled frame.
3. **Upper and lower roller:** The essential part of the calendar, the distance between them determines the calendaring gap.
4. **IR lamp:** Not included. Optional component to preheat the substrate before it enters the calendaring gap. Max temperature is 200°C.
5. **Gap adjustment gear box:** It changes the speed and direction of the rotation applied to the Gap adjustment handles to move the lower roller up and down.
6. **Gap adjustment handles.** Rotating both handles in **counter clockwise direction** lowers the lower roller. Rotating the handles in clockwise direction moves the lower roller up.
7. **Unprocessed coated foil:** The depicted foil or electrode rests in the loading tray in the inlet side of the machine.
8. **Handles rotation lock.** Consists of two hand screws to prevent or allow the rotation of the gap adjustment handles.
9. **Force measurement sensors.** One in each side on the upper roller measure the force during calendaring.

The following image shows the outlet side of the machine.

Figure 3-2: Outlet side of machine. GUI not shown for explanatory reasons

1. **Outlet side protective covers.** Two independent metallic covers that should be removed only when the machine is power off and disconnected from the electricity supply for cleaning purposes after work.
2. **Lower laser sensors.** Used for measuring the relative distance between the sensor and the lower roller surface.
3. **Gear motor.** Is a torque multiplier and speed reduction gearbox to achieve a wide range of calendaring speeds.

With the FOM Standalone Calendaring unit, an accompanying electrical cabinet is included.

Figure 3-3: Labeled photo of the FOM Stand-alone Calendaring unit electrical cabinet. Dimensions (DxWxH) = 600x1000x960 mm

1. **GUI:** This is the Graphic User Interface of the calendaring unit.
2. **Internet port.** This port is used to provide internet to the Calendaring unit for remote support.
3. **Machine ethernet port:** This port is used to establish communication with the machine, only to be used by FOM service team.
4. **Main power switch.** It is the main and only power switch of the Calendaring unit. Used to reset the machine and power it ON and OFF.

3.2. Calendaring unit dimensions

Figure 2-4. Top view calendaring machine

Figure 2-5. Front view calendaring machine

4. Installation

The following section describes the recommended procedure for safe installation and operation of the FOM Standalone Calendaring unit coater.

4.1. Safety precautions

Important: Before beginning any work with the FOM Standalone Calendaring unit coater, operators should read the Disclaimers and equipment hazards in Section 1.6.16 and ensure that they have taken the following safety precautions:

- Familiarize with the contents of this user manual and ensure a comprehensive understanding of its instructions.
- The equipment should be exclusively used in accordance with the instructions provided in this user manual. Engaging in unintended applications or making aftermarket modifications to the equipment not only carries the risk of equipment damage but also poses a threat to operator safety. It is important to note that such actions will void the warranty provided for the equipment.
- Operators must wear appropriate PPE when operating the tool, including safety glasses, a lab coat, safety gloves (such as nitrile gloves), a laboratory cap, and any additional PPE as dictated by the materials and applications used (e.g., anti-static coat for hazardous nanomaterials or clean room work).
- Refrain from operating the machine while wearing loose clothing, wristbands, or having long, unrestrained hair, as they may become entangled in the moving parts of the equipment.
- Position the machine in a well-ventilated area to prevent operator exposure to volatile solvents and aerosolized materials.
- Ensure that no objects obstruct the path of any moving components at any time, as this could compromise both the machine's functionality and operator safety.

An emergency stop button is available on the machine's GUI panel. Pressing this button promptly ceases all machine operations and movements, ensuring a "safe" state. To restore regular machine operations, the physical button must be reset, the software engaged, and the alarms reset.

Important: Emergency stop buttons must be assessed once per year to ensure their functionality.

4.2. Machine installation

Important: Lifting the machine incorrectly or with inadequate lifting capacity can result in personal injury or equipment damage. Exercise caution and ensure the machine is stabilized during lifting to prevent accidental tilting.

4.2.1. Lifting and levelling

Lifting the Machine

The standalone calendaring unit, including the machine and the electrical cabinet, must be moved using appropriate lifting equipment. **The lifting eye bolts on the top base plate are not intended for the customer's use.** Instead, use a forklift or similar equipment to safely lift and position the entire unit in the desired location. Ensure that the machine is lifted securely to avoid any tipping or damage.

Leveling the machine

The standalone unit is mounted on a frame equipped with adjustable feet, allowing easy adjustment to ensure the machine is level and stable.

Adjusting the height.

Figure 3-1. Feet position on the calendaring machine

You can adjust the feet to raise or lower the machine for leveling. You can turn the adjustment wheel by hand or use a 17mm wrench for more precise control. The feet can be adjusted by up to 12 mm.

Figure 3-2. Adjusting the feet by hand and with the wrench

Locking the feet

After adjusting the feet to achieve a leveling accuracy of 1 mm/m, lower the feet to lock the machine securely in place. This ensures that the machine remains stable during operation.

Check for stability

Once the machine is in position and leveled, verify that all feet are appropriately adjusted and that the machine is stable on the ground without rocking or shaking. Proper leveling ensures smooth operation and prevents unnecessary wear on the machine components.

Removal of bearing protection

The bearings supporting the two rollers are protected against damage from transportation by the use of a simple clamping sheet as shown below.

This clamping sheet must be removed before operation of the machine can be conducted.

Lower the lower roller by rotating both handles in the counterclockwise direction. Remove then the protective clamping sheet.

4.2.2. Connecting the machine

The FOM Standalone calendaring unit requires minimal setup for a power connection. Before connecting the machine, ensure that the main power switch on the electrical cabinet is set to the "OFF" position. Do not supply power during installation. Connect the main power cable from the FOM Standalone Calendaring Unit to the nearest suitable power outlet.

Figure 3-3. Main power switch in the OFF position (left); main power cable (right)

The FOM Technologies calendaring unit has been successfully installed.

4.2.3. Powering on the tool

To power on the tool, turn the physical power switch on the machine's front to the "On" position. The internal electronics of the electrical cabinet should light up, indicating that power is being supplied. It may take several minutes for the electrical cabinet to fully boot.

Figure 3-4. Main power switch in the ON position

5. Control interface

The FOM Stand-alone Calendaring unit comes equipped with an intuitive and user-friendly interface that provides convenient control over all the tool's functions. This interface enables users to manage various aspects of the tool, such as calendaring speed, gap size, jog speed and max. allowed force. The following sections provide detailed explanations of the functions available on each screen of the Graphic User Interface (GUI), and a description of the hardware buttons panel.

5.1. Hardware buttons panel

This set of physical buttons includes the most common actions performed during the calendaring process, including an emergency stop button. The functions of these buttons are described below (see also Figure 5-1):

Figure 5-1: GUI, hardware and software buttons panel.

1. **GUI:** This is the Graphic User Interface of the calendaring unit.
2. **Indication light:** Green, running. Orange, action needed. Red, present error.
3. **Physical buttons:** They mirror the software buttons on top of them
 - F1: Jog forward.** It moves the rollers in the calendaring direction, the electrode would move away from the user.
 - F2: Force Data screen** where the user can read the current Process Force Left, Right and adjust the Machine Stop Force set point.
 - F3: Gap Data screen** showing the calendaring gap and rolls position information coming from the laser's readouts.
 - F4: Operation screen** to start and stop the movement of the Calendar rollers.
 - F5: Settings screen** to set the jog speed.
 - F6: Alarms screen** shows current and previous alarms.
 - F7: Engage Software button.** When pressed the software button turns green meaning that the machine can be controlled by the software.
 - F8: Software power ON/OFF button.** If pressed it will close the software. If the software is not running press the start button (only visible when the software is not running).
4. **Emergency stop:** When pressed, immediately stops all ongoing operations and cuts power in case of danger.

5.2. Stand-alone Calendaring unit software interface

The Stand alone Calendaring unit is controlled only through a Graphic User Interface (GUI).

5.2.1. F2: Force Data screen

Figure 5-2. F2: Force data screen

It shows the process force measured in the upper roller in kN on each side. Only when there is material in the calendaring gap you will have a force read out (current force). **Do not lift the lower roller to the extent it touches the upper roller.**

If the current force read out is greater or equal to the Machine Stop Force the rotation will stop and an Alarm will appear in the Alarm screen accompanied with red indication light. In that case you can increase the gap with the Gap adjustment handles, go to Alarms screen and acknowledge the alarm then go to operation screen and continue calendaring or, press F1: Jog Forward to move out the electrode (towards the user) from the calendaring gap.

In Force Data Screen you can also see the relative distance (after zeroing) between the lowest point of the bottom roll and the right and left lasers. This information is useful when calibrating the calendaring gap.

5.2.2. F3: Gap data screen

Figure 5-3. F3: Gap data screen

Gap data screen shows the absolute and relative distance (after zeroing) between **the lowest point of the bottom roller surface** and the right and left lasers. It also shows the absolute and relative distance (after zeroing) between **the upper point of the top roller surface** and the right and left lasers.

Knowing the relative position of the rollers the screen shows the Actual (current) gap Left and Right values in μm . The Actual (current) gap should be calibrated using the Initial gap set point field and a feeler gauge of known thickness. Look Gap Calibration section.

The relative position of the 4 lasers can be Zeroed by touching the Zero lasers button.

To increase the Gap: Rotate both handles in **counter clockwise direction**. It lowers only the lower roller.

To reduce the Gap: Rotating the handles in **clockwise direction**. It moves only the lower roller up.

5.2.3. F4: Operation screen

Figure 5-4. F4: Operation screen

From this screen the **rotation** of the upper roller can be **started or stopped** in the forward direction (the electrode would move away from the user), or it can also be Jog in reverse (to move the electrode towards the user) or Jog forward. Notice that the bottom roller is passive and will only follow the top roller rotation if there is an electrode in the gap producing friction against it.

In the Web Speed field the user can input the calendaring speed set point from 0.1 to 2 m/min.

5.2.4. F5: Settings screen

Figure 5-5. F5: Settings screen

In this screen the user can input the Jog speed for both forward and reverse. The factory reset button resets the jog speed to its default value.

5.2.5. F6: Alarms screen

Figure 5-6. F6: Alarms screen

The upper part of the Alarms or Notifications screen shows the current alarms in case there are any. The lower part of the screen shows the log of the previous alarms.

When an alarm is triggered, the indication light will turn red, and a popup window will appear on top of any open screen.

To clear an alarm:

1. Close the popup window showing the alarm by touching the X in the upper right corner then,
2. Restore the parameter that caused the alarm (e.g. Max Force reached due to a too small gap)
3. Go to Alarms screen and touching the Acknowledge button.

6. Operating instructions

Once the machine is correctly installed, powered up and the software interface is engaged to the tool, then the user must calibrate the gap before starting a calendaring process. Please follow the operating instructions below.

6.1. Turning ON the calendaring unit.

1. Connect the power cable to the electricity supply.
2. Position the main switch in ON position
3. After a few seconds the unit will initialize, and the software will auto launch and appear in the Graphic User Interface (GUI).

Important: Make sure all protective covers are in place before engaging the software.

6.2. Turning OFF and cleaning the calendaring unit.

1. Remove any material or electrode in the calendaring gap using the controls in Operation screen.
2. In the GUI touch F8: Software power ON/OFF button. It will power off the control software.
3. Position the **main switch in OFF position.**
4. **Disconnect the power cable from the electricity supply.**
5. Remove the two protective covers on the Unloading side to get access to the rollers.
6. Clean the rollers with a soft tissue and water or IPA. You can activate the rotation of the top roll touching the Start/Stop or Jog buttons in Operation screen. The bottom roll can be rotated by hand.
7. **If you are in the unloading side of the Calendaring unit, make sure no one is manipulating the touch screen out of your sight!**
8. Put the two protective covers back in place.

Important: Make sure the machine is power OFF and the power cable is disconnected from the electricity supply.

Important: Make sure the rollers are cleaned and there is no material or electrode in the calendaring gap

6.3. Calendaring gap calibration

This section describes the recommended steps to calibrate the calendaring gap.

Important: It is crucial to avoid any direct touch between the rollers to prevent damaging them compromising the quality of calendaring results.

Important: It is recommended that when using narrow feeler gauges they are inserted on the edges of the rolls not in the center in order to avoid scratching it. Insert picture of tool. When the feeler gauge is inserted do not do sudden movements, only slow and calculated movements.

1. Go to Gap Data screen by pressing the Gap Data button
2. Using the gap adjustment handles to **lower the lower roller (or increase the gap) by rotating both of the handles in counter clockwise direction.**
 - a. You can follow the movement of the roll by looking at the Absolute value.
 - b. The lowest bottom position is around +30 mm
3. Position your feeler gauge tool of known thickness (e.g. 100 μm) in between the rollers **from the unloading side**. It should enter the gap with no friction, and you should be able to see it from the loading side of the machine. If you cannot place the feeler gauge tool in the gap between the rollers increase the gap by lowering the **lower roller by rotating the handles in the counter clockwise direction.**

4. When the feeler gauge is placed in the gap between the rollers Go to Force Data screen.
5. Lift the **lower roller up by rotating the handles in the clockwise direction.**
 - a. In Force Data screen you can see the Absolute Right and Left position of the bottom roller.
 - b. The Absolute Right and Left position of the lower roller should decrease as you lift it up by operating both handles.
6. When you start to see a Process Force Right and Left of approx. 0.1 kN, make a $\frac{1}{4}$ of a turn on each handle still in the clockwise direction.
 - a. Do not make full turns of the handles, instead move the lower roller up in small increments.
 - b. At this point the feeler gauge should be locked by the compression force.
7. Go to Gap Data screen and write the thickness of the feeler gauge in the Initial gap Set point field.
 - a. Notice that the units are μm .
8. Click Zero Lasers
 - a. It will reset the relative position of the 4 lasers and establish the Actual (current) gap equal to the filler gauge thickness.
9. Lower the lower roller by operating the handles two revolutions in the **counter clockwise direction.**
 - a. You will see that the Actual(current) gap value increases.
10. Take the feeler gauge outside the calendaring gap and store it carefully.
11. Now you can set the calendaring gap you want to use using the gap adjustment handles and the Actual (current) gap read out in the Gap Data Screen.

6.4. Getting started with calendaring

The FOM Standalone Calendaring unit is compatible with a wide variety of flexible substrates. This section describes the recommended steps to calendar materials.

1. Measure the pre-calendaring thickness of the electrode.
2. Go to Gap Data screen and using the handles, set the gap you want to use in the Current Left and Right field.
 - a. **Moving the handles clock wise reduces the gap.**
 - b. Take into consideration the pre-calendaring thickness of your electrode. A too small gap might require more force than the Max Force setting in Load Measurements screen.
3. Lock the handles using the handles' rotation lock (Figure 3-1)
4. Go to Operation screen and set the speed.
5. We need to make sure the substrate leaves the machine and comes out in the unloading side of the machine. Press start and introduce your electrode by the loading side of the unit (facing the screen).
 - a. If your electrode does not come easy in the unloading side, press stop and then press Jog Reverse to take your electrode back.
 - b. Use a sacrificial electrode or plastic stripe guide to which you can tape your electrode and guide it to the unloading side.
 - c. You might need to increase the gap to introduce the guide.
 - d. Set the calendaring gap and press start again.
6. If Max Force Alarm is triggered, increase the calendaring gap.

Important: Make sure you clean the rollers with a soft tissue and water or IPA after working. Do not leave the rollers wet.

7. Troubleshooting

7.1. Alarms

Possible alarm errors and solutions from the Notification Screen panel:

Emergency stop tripped	Release the e-stop button Acknowledge the notification and re-engage the software
Drive system fault	Increase the calendaring gap Acknowledge the notification and re-engage the software
Max force reached	Increase the calendaring gap Increase the max force set point if possible. Acknowledge the notification and re-engage the software

8. Service and maintenance

In the event of a failure, please contact FOM Technologies A/S to coordinate the necessary actions. Opening the device should only be done by authorized personnel from FOM Technologies A/S or their authorized service staff. Any unauthorized attempts to open or repair the device may void warranty claims.

The FOM Standalone Calendaring unit is designed to be easy to use, with little need for complex maintenance. However, observing the following standard maintenance steps during daily use will result in the most ideal performance and longevity of your unit.

- 1. Cleaning and Inspection:** Clean any material from the rollers using appropriate solvents. Ensure no residues are left behind. Conduct a thorough visual inspection of all components. Check for signs of wear, damage, or misalignment. Tighten any loose fasteners.
- 2. Safety Checks:** Regularly assess the emergency stop functionality to ensure it operates effectively. Ensure all safety guards, interlocks, and sensors are functioning as intended.